

PREDICTION OF THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE COMPOSITE WITH TIME-SERIES EXTERNAL AND TECHNICAL FACTORS USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Indonesia Stock Exchange Composite is an indicative of the movement of all stocks traded on Indonesia stock exchange. Investor uses this to measure the level of capital gains and benchmark the investment portfolio performance. Accurate prediction of stock market composite remains a challenging task, particularly in emerging markets where external economic factors such as interest rates of central bank, world oil prices, inflation rates, and USD/IDR exchange rate exert significant influence. Existing research in prediction models using artificial neural network often focus on specific stocks and overlook the combined influence of macroeconomic and technical indicators. This research addresses the gap by exploring artificial neural network models to predict the stock exchange composite price by integrates composite technical indicators with external macroeconomic factors. Cross-industry standard process for data mining uses as framework to guide the development. Secondary time-series data period 2019 to 2024 of each factors taken. Empirical results demonstrate that the Neural Net model achieve high predictive accuracy and outperform Deep Learning model. The findings highlight the effectiveness of combining macroeconomic and technical factors in data mining processing with artificial neural network for composite price forecasting and offer practical implications for investors and analysts in emerging markets.

Keywords: *IDX Composite, Stock, Artificial Neural Network, Artificial Intelligence, CRISP-DM*

1 INTRODUCTION

The Indonesia Stock Exchange Composite Index (IDX Composite) is the main indices of the capital market on Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). It tracks changes in the stock prices of all preferred and ordinary stocks listed on the IDX. The IDX Composite calculation is carried out every day after the close of trading on each working day. Stock trading fluctuations are very unstable (volatile), complex, and basically very dynamic. Fluctuations occur along with the process of bargaining for the value of a stock and the process of buying and selling (trading) of a stock by investors. Investors can analyze the value of stocks through technical analysis techniques and fundamental analysis [1]. The analysis process also considers internal factors such as company financial reports, company performance, stock price trends, sector trends of a stock, and price-to-earning (PE) ratio. External factors can also affect the value of stocks and the

IDX Composite, namely: market analysis sentiment, political economic situation, global political economic situation, exchange rates, national bank interest rates, international benchmark interest rates (US central bank interest rates The Fed), inflation rates, oil prices, and other factors [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

Stock price indexes have the following main benefits [7]: (1) to calculate total return performance and aggregate market risk measures over a certain period of time, (2) to create portfolios that follow index performance, (3) to predict index prices based on historical changes in index prices, (4) as a benchmark for assessing the performance of professional financial managers.

The Financial Services Authority of Indonesia (OJK) also explained that the stock index functions as an indicator that describes market conditions in a trading period. From the index investors can explore the trend of stock price movements, for example

when stock price index moves up, usually most of stock prices in the index also often increase [7]. With these benefits, investors need a way to predict the IDX Composite based on the dynamics of the factors that influenced it.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) which is a popular technique of regression prediction in Machine Learning (ML) [8] has been used in predicting stock price. Unlike previous research that mostly use ANN for predicting specific stocks price, this research proposes a novel use of ANN to build prediction models using Neural Network model and Deep Learning Model to predict IDX Composite price based on combined composite technical factors and external factors that influenced it by exchange rates, interest rates, inflation, and oil prices.

Research will use CRISP-DM methodology which give an arranged approach to conducting projects of data mining [9]. This methodology composed of six steps: started with understanding the business followed by understanding data of variables, then third is data pre-processing, after data ready then the model building process, after that testing and evaluation of the model, and at last is deployment phase. Followings are the research questions (RQ) of this study:

RQ-1: How to forecast the IDX Composite utilizing technical time-series data and external factor data (national central bank interest rates, oil prices, exchange rates, and inflation) using artificial neural network (ANN).

RQ-2: How accurate the models are?

This research paper will be structured starting from the introduction, literature review, methodology, result and discussion, findings, and research conclusions. Results of this research study will be beneficial as reference of model for solution to predict IDX Composite prices.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Stock, Composite Index, Analysis, and Factors Affecting

Share is a financial instrument that represents a proportional ownership claim on the company's assets, income, and liabilities [10]. Stock investment has benefit from capital gain when selling prices higher than purchased price, secondly from dividends which part of company's income that is the right of the shareholder [11]. Conversely shares have capital loss and liquidation risk.

Capital market is a market formed to trade shares amongst securities institutions and investors. Stock traded through licensed securities companies where investors placing buy order stating stock name,

nominal lots, price; and the opposite investors placing sell order specified stock name, lots, desired price; when matched then trade happens [7]. Market fluctuates in real time due to supply, demand, fundamental factors, technical factors, macro-economic factors, and non-economic factors that affect stock values [5].

Factors that influence stock are central bank interest rate, inflation, currency exchange, and world oil [2], [4], [5], [6]. Interest rate issued by central bank of Indonesia called BI-Rate is one of instruments used to keep the country's macroeconomic stability [12]. Inflation is an overall rise in the prices of basic needs for society [13]. Currency's value in relation to another is known as the exchange rate [14]. USD/IDR is Rupiah value in relation to the US dollar. When foreign currency exchange market preferred by investors, the stock investment will decline [15]. World oil price is the USD monetary value assigned to acquire one barrel of crude oil, generally using West Texas Intermediate (WTI) oil [16].

All stocks listed on the IDX have their price performance measured by the composite index price that calculated daily after trading is closed. Index calculated using Market Value Weighted Average Index using following formula (1) [17].

$$Index = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Market\ Cap_i}{Base\ Market\ Cap} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Stock analysis process can be done through fundamental and technical analysis [1]. From the analyses investors can read the market performance and see if it's experiencing an increase (bullish), or a decrease (bearish) [11].

2.2 Data Mining, Artificial Neural Network, and CRISP-DM

Data Mining is a term for extract knowledge from data that has large amount, this term can also be called mining knowledge or finding knowledge [9]. Technically, Data Mining process utilize techniques of statistics, mathematics, and artificial intelligence (AI) to identify and extract useful information, knowledge, and patterns from very large data sources [9].

Generally, Data Mining is used to recognize the following main pattern types: Association, Prediction, Clusters, and Sequential relationships. Using historical data, Classification can be used to predict future outcomes. When the prediction is a class label (eg: rain, sunny) it is called a Classification prediction problem, and when the prediction is a numeric number (eg temperature

degrees, stock value of goods) it is called a Regression prediction problem [9]. There are 2 stages of methodology in Classification Prediction, namely developing a model through training and testing/deploying the model through testing. In assessing the model, the following factors must be considered: predictive accuracy, speed, robustness, scalability, and interpretability [9]. There are several algorithms that can be used to perform Prediction Classification modeling, namely one of which is the Neural Network which is a popular technique from Machine Learning (ML) techniques that can perform problem classification. Then in Prediction Regression modeling there are the following algorithms [9]: Regression Trees, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Linear or Non-linear Regression, k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), as well as Genetic Algorithms (GA). Data mining learning techniques can have two categories as follow: supervised, and unsupervised. On supervised learning the descriptive attributes (independent or determining variables) and the class attributes (output variables or result variables) will be defined on the training data. On unsupervised Learning, only descriptive attributes are included on the training data. The Supervised learning type is used in Data Mining Prediction/Classification, Regression, and Time series.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are computational technologies created to replicate how the human brain works [9]. The machines function with ambiguous data and have simultaneous memory storage, a neural network is another name for it. From the explanation, we can conclude that ANN is a computer technology that make computers able to emulate human brain, namely processing information simultaneously and utilizing memory.

Cross-industry process for data mining (CRISP-DM) is the standard for data mining operations which provides approach in structured [9]. The structured six-steps in CRISP-DM are: (1) Understanding of Business, (2) Understanding of Data, (3) Data Preparation, (4) Building the Model, (5) Testing and Evaluation, and (6) Deployment.

2.3 Stock Trading Applications in Indonesia

Currently, there are several well-known online trading and stock information applications in Indonesia that have been licensed by the OJK as follows: IDX Channel, IPOT, Bareksa, Bibit, Ajaib, Emtrade, Stockbit, BCAS Best Mobile, MOST, POEMS ID, BIONS, Tanamduit, SimInvest. Exploration of these applications has generally not revealed the use of AI in the features that anticipate a stock's price, including the IDX Composite's close

price, based on a variety of variables that may impact the stock.

2.4 Research on Existing Paper

There is much related research on how ML used to predict stock prices, including what factors are affecting it. One proposed a combination deep learning (DL) model called ResNLS, which integrates long short-term memory (LSTM), residual, and recurrent neural network (RNN) techniques [18]. This model demonstrated the best performance in predicting stock closing prices using data from the past five trading days.

Another utilized a hybrid deep learning model combining recurrent and LSTM neural networks with Word2Vec natural language processing (NLP), revealing that inputs and news headlines significantly influence stock movement direction predictions [19].

Another employed time series forecasting using RNN and the Holt-Winters algorithm (HWA), concluding that combining trend forecasting, machine learning (ML), and recommendation systems is advantageous [20].

Another research does integrate LSTM and convolutional neural networks (CNN) to process news headlines and stock technical data, resulting in highly accurate stock open price predictions [21].

Another research does apply an ML model using the "M5P model tree" algorithm, incorporating stock intrinsic values and health indices into a Financial Decision Support System (DSS) [22]. Their results provided reliable stock portfolio recommendations with optimal short- and long-term returns.

Another research explored ML techniques using random forest (RF) and artificial neural networks (ANN) for regression and classification, with the ANN model successfully predicting stock prices close to their actual values [23].

Another research employed support vector regression (SVR) with a radial basis function (RBF) and polynomial linear regression, yielding good predictive performance [24].

There are also related research that investigates factors that affecting IDX Composite. First research uses multi-linear regression analysis with software tools to demonstrate that the IDX Composite is influenced by inflation, BI-Rate, and USD/IDR exchange rates [2]. Another research does analyze 2005-2016 composite data and found that Dow Jones Industrial average and world crude oil price had a positive effect on IDX Composite while USD/IDR exchange rate had negative effect [5]. Another research applied F-test using SPSS on data from 1990 to 2020 and found that inflation, interest rate,

and broad money negatively influence IDX Composite [6].

In contrast with previous related research described that using ML for predicting specific stocks price, this research will focus on building ML model using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to predict the stocks composite of IDX based on composite technical factors and external factors that influence it.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research approach grounded in the CRISP-DM (Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining) methodology, which structures the research into six sequential stages: Business Understanding, Data Understanding, Data Preparation, Modeling, Evaluation, and Deployment. Its implementation is depicted in *Figure 1* and will be explain further.

Figure 1 CRISP-DM Stages

The core research question is centered on predicting the closing price of the IDX Composite using artificial neural networks (ANN), based on both time-series technical data and external macroeconomic indicators such as interest rates, oil prices, exchange rates, and inflation. The study utilizes data spanning from July 2019 to July 2024, with analysis conducted using RapidMiner AI Studio and Microsoft Excel on a MacBook Pro. The CRISP-DM framework ensures a structured and iterative process, guiding each step from problem formulation to final insights. The results will be analyzed and discussed with reference to the original research objectives, with conclusions and recommendations provided.

3.1 Business Understanding

At this stage, an understanding of the background of the process at the IDX in calculating the composite prices will be explained. A review of related literature is then used to comprehend the factors that influence the IDX Composite closing price. Then will also explained on how the IDX Composite can be used by investors in measuring investment portfolios. This understanding will then support the research in exploring the creation of ANN models for predicting the IDX Composite closing price based on those factors.

3.2 Data Understanding

Moving to Data Understanding, the required datasets are identified, including technical indicators and macroeconomic variables such as the BI Rate, inflation, currency exchange rates, and oil prices. This stage is crucial for recognizing data quality, identifying potential issues such as missing or inconsistent values, and gaining insights into the structure of the input data. It ensures that the subsequent preparation stage is grounded in a thorough comprehension of data sources and characteristics. Understanding the nature of the data helps shape preprocessing strategies and informs model selection.

3.3 Data Preprocessing (Preparation)

The Data Preparation stage involves cleaning, transforming, and organizing the data into a format suitable for modeling. Key tasks include consolidating data from various sources, handling missing or duplicate values, normalizing numerical features, and reducing dimensionality. This process results in a final dataset ready for analysis and is often iterative, requiring multiple passes based on feedback from later stages. This step plays a pivotal role in the CRISP-DM cycle, as data quality directly impacts model performance and reliability.

3.4 Model Building.

During the Modeling phase, ANN algorithms are implemented using Rapidminer AI Studio as shown on **Error! Reference source not found.** the software provides predictive model operator Neural Net (NN) **Error! Reference source not found.** and Deep Learning (DL) Figure 3. The Neural Net uses a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with backpropagation, while the Deep Learning model from H2O incorporates advanced techniques such as stochastic gradient descent, dropout, and adaptive learning.

These models are trained on the prepared dataset using a simple data-split estimation methodology to

generate training and testing subsets [9]. CRISP-DM recognizes that modeling may loop back to earlier stages, and in this study, model performance may inform refinements in data preparation or selection.

Figure 2 ANN Algorithms Neural Net

Figure 3 ANN Algorithms Deep Learning

After the process of split dataset, then the training dataset will be utilized in the process of building models using the neural net and deep learning algorithms.

3.5 Testing and evaluation

In the 5th step of CRISP-DM process will continue with testing the model being built using test dataset, then evaluation will be carried out. A loss function or error function then will be used to measure the model's performance, namely using the calculations in Table 1.

Table 1 Loss Function or Error Function Formula

Loss Function or Error Function	Formula
Root Mean Squared Error	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}}$
Mean Absolute Error	$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \hat{y}_i $
Mean Squared Error	$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$
Mean Absolute Percentage Error	$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right $

Where:

- y_i = the actual value.
- \hat{y}_i = the predicted value.
- n = the number of samples in the dataset

These metrics help determine how closely the predicted values align with actual values, allowing researchers to gauge the model's effectiveness in answering the research question. If the performance is insufficient, insights from this phase may trigger a

return to earlier steps for adjustments, as CRISP-DM promotes iterative refinement.

3.5.1 Deployment

Finally, the Deployment phase presents the findings and contextualizes the results within the scope of the initial objectives and the reviewed literature. The study discusses the predictive performance of the models, their practical implications for stock price forecasting, and any limitations encountered.

This final stage also includes conclusions and offers directions for future research, emphasizing the continuous and cyclical nature of CRISP-DM in real-world data mining projects.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In general, chapter 4 will discuss the application of research methods including each step of CRISP-DM. Then in the Testing and Evaluation step, testing will be carried out on the model using testing datasets (30% of the data) to evaluate the regression performance. The results will then be explained further.

4.1 Data Collection

Before entering the data mining stage, it's required to collect each research variable data from each data source. The data period required in this study is period from July-2019 until July 2024.

IDX Composite technical variable and USD/IDR exchange rate variable data was taken from secondary data sources on the Yahoo Finance [25]. World oil price, WTI (West Texas Intermediate), variable data was taken from the Investing.com website [26]. The BI-Rate variable data and Indonesia inflation rate were taken from secondary data sources through the Bank Indonesia website [27] [28].

All these secondary data sources provide data download facilities in the form of comma separated values (CSV). The total data required in the study is 1,825 rows of data calculated from the total days in 5 years from July-2019 to July-2024 (365 days multiplied by 5 years).

4.2 Business Understanding

IDX Composite is the main index of the IDX which assesses the price performance of each stock listed on the stock market. Index shows the increase or decreases investment on the stock market [11]. Stock prices including the composite prices can be affected by factors like exchange rates, interest rates, inflation rates, world oil prices, socio-political conditions, and economic conditions factors [2], [3], [5], [6]. Figure 4 illustrate this. Index price

prediction based on these factors can complement information for investors in managing investment portfolios [1].

The application of ANN algorithms to predict has been widely used before Predictive analytics with classification regression and ANN algorithms can be used to discover patterns in historical data and make predictions of composite price.

Figure 4 Technical Factors and External Factors Affecting IDX Composite

This study will explore a data mining model using ANN algorithm to predict the IDX Composite closing price based on the composite technical factors and the external factors that influence it.

4.3 Data Understanding

Variables data collected and the attributes of research variables explained in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Variables that are the focus of the research

Variables Attributes	Explanation	Data Type
Date	Data identification using date.	Date
Technical IDX Composite		
Open	price at the opening	Decimal
Close	price at the closing	Decimal
High	highest price during the trading	Decimal
Low	lowest price during the trading	Decimal
Volume	number of shares traded in trading	Numeric
Bank indonesia		
BI-7Day-RR	interest rate from Bank Indonesia	Decimal
Inflation	continuous rate prices increase of basic needs	Decimal
Currency USD/IDR		
Close	price of USD/IDR exchange rate	Decimal
Worldwide Crude Oil Price		
Price	USD price to obtain one barrel of crude oil	Decimal

These variables will then become independent variables in creating the prediction model. Each variable's data will be presented as historical time-series data depending on dates. Then the variable that is the target of the model prediction (variable Y) is the Close variable from the IDX Composite technical data.

4.4 Data Preparation

Next is data pre-processing step that will prepare the datasets. Followings are the procedures:

4.4.1 Data consolidation and data cleaning

This section will explain the data consolidation steps combined with the optional data cleaning steps carried out according to the findings in the variable data. Processes are as follows:

1. Variables data are collected from source and explained in Table 3. Total data is 1,825 rows represent daily data in 5 years from July-2019 to July-2024.

Table 3 Data Collection

Variabels	Data Source and Format	Data Period	Data Collection Method
Technical IDX Composite	Secondary: Web Yahoo Finance Format: comma separated values (CSV)	1-July-2019 to 1-July-2024	Download data by researcher
Exchange Rate of USD/IDR	Secondary: Web Investing. Format: CSV		
World Oil Prices	Secondary: Web Bank Indonesia Format: Microsoft Excel		
BI-Rate			
Inflation Rate of Indonesia			

Figure 5 Data Collection

2. Data selection (feature selection) is performed on each raw data collected with the aim of only taking the variables needed in the study. The selection process uses the "Select Attributes" operator in the Rapidminer software to select attributes from the list of attributes available in the raw data (the Attributes box on the left side of the Select Attributes modal UI). The Figure 6 is the attribute selection process on the IDX Composite technical raw data. The selected

attributes are: Close, Date, High, Low, Open, Volume.

Figure 6 Attribute Selection Technical IDX Composite

Figure 7 show is the selected attributes for USD/IDR exchange rates which are: Close, Date. Then the Close attribute is renamed to USDIDR.

Figure 7 Attribute Selection Data USD/IDR Currency Rate

Figure 8 show the selected attributes for world oil prices, there are: Date, Price. Then the Price attribute is renamed to BrentOilPrice.

Figure 8 Attribute Selection Data Crude Oil Price

BI-Rate data required impute values with dates from 1-July-2019 to 1-July-2024 refer from BI-Rate source values. Processed using Microsoft Excel VLOOKUP, Table 4 shows the source values used for imputes values to the new format Table 5, BI-7Day-RR attribute then selected for dataset.

Table 4 BI-Rate sample source values

NO	Date	BI-7Day-RR
61	20 Juni 2019	6.00%
60	18 Juli 2019	5.75%
59	22 Agustus 2019	5.50%

Table 5 BI-Rate data cleaning imputed values

Date	BI-7Day-RR
7/1/19	6.00%
7/2/19	6.00%
7/3/19	6.00%
7/4/19	6.00%
7/5/19	6.00%
...	...

The following Figure 9 is the process of selecting attributes on the BI-Rate raw data after data processing. The selected attributes are date and bi-7day-rr.

Figure 9 Attribute Selection Data BI-Rate

Indonesia inflation rate data required data cleaning processing impute values so that it can become datasets with daily values across dates 1-July-2019 to 1-July-2024. Processing is done using Microsoft Excel's VLOOKUP function of the raw data table that has been sorted ascending. The following Table 6 is data processing from the raw data source of the inflation rate to a new format Table 7.

Table 6 Inflation data source values

No	Period	Inflation Rate
61	June-2019	3.28%
60	July-2019	3.32%
59	August-2019	3.49%
58	September-2019	3.39%
57	October-2019	3.13%
56	November-2019	3%

Table 7 Inflation data cleaning imputes values

date	inflation-rate
7/1/19	3.32%
7/2/19	3.32%
7/3/19	3.32%
...	...
8/1/19	3.49%
...	...
9/1/19	3.39%
...	...

The following Figure 10 is the process of selecting attributes on the Indonesia inflation rate data. The selected attributes are date and inflation-rate.

Figure 10 Attribute Selection Data Inflation Rate

3. Integrate data. The next step is to integrate/merge all data sources using a commonality "date" attribute/column across all data sources. Figure 11 is the Rapidminer visualization design to merge all datasets into 1 main dataset for research. The results of the process of combining all the data to become 1 dataset then can be used for the model building process. From the statistical analysis on Figure 12, it is known that the Volume attribute has 1

missing value, so it is necessary to add a data pre-processing impute values function to fill in the data. Figure 13 showing the impute process and Figure 14 show the results after imputing values are performed.

Then continued with the analysis of the relationship between variables using either scatter plot or using the correlation matrix table. Figure 15 shows the results of the scatter plot graphic visualization between variables using Rapidminer software.

Figure 11 Rapidminer Process Design

The screenshot shows the 'Statistics' tab in Rapidminer. The main table displays the following data:

Name	Type	Missing	Statistics	Filter (10 / 10 attributes):
▼ Date	Date	0	Earliest date: Jul 1, 2019; Latest date: Jun 28, 2024; Duration: 1824 days	Search for Attribute
▼ Open	Real	0	Min: 3937.632; Max: 7422.302; Average: 6394.675	
▼ High	Real	0	Min: 4123.562; Max: 7454.448; Average: 6428.878	
▼ Low	Real	0	Min: 3911.716; Max: 7392.011; Average: 6354.928	
▼ Close	Real	0	Min: 3937.632; Max: 7433.315; Average: 6391.979	
▼ Volume	Integer	1	Min: 20620000; Max: 615071900; Average: 154224838.182	
▼ USDIDR	Real	0	Min: 13213.240; Max: 16504.801; Average: 14769.164	
▼ BrentOilPrice	Real	0	Min: 19.330; Max: 127.980; Average: 73.435	
▼ bi-7day-rr	Real	0	Min: 0.035; Max: 0.062; Average: 0.046	
▼ inflation-rate	Real	0	Min: 0.013; Max: 0.059; Average: 0.029	

Showing attributes 1 - 10. Examples: 1,211. Special Attributes: 0. Regular Attributes: 10.

Figure 12 Research Dataset Statistics Analysis

Figure 13 Rapidminer Process Impute Values

The screenshot shows the 'Results' view in Rapidminer. The 'Statistics' tab is active, displaying a table of statistics for the dataset. The table includes columns for Name, Type, Missing, Statistics, and Filter. The statistics are as follows:

Name	Type	Missing	Statistics	Filter (10 / 10 attributes)
Date	Date	0	Earliest date: Jul 1, 2019 Latest date: Jun 28, 2024 Duration: 1824 days	
Open	Real	0	Min: 3937.632 Max: 7422.302 Average: 6394.675	
High	Real	0	Min: 4123.562 Max: 7454.448 Average: 6428.878	
Low	Real	0	Min: 3911.716 Max: 7392.011 Average: 6354.928	
Close	Real	0	Min: 3937.632 Max: 7433.315 Average: 6391.979	
Volume	Integer	0	Min: 20620000 Max: 615071900 Average: 154269538.757	
USDIDR	Real	0	Min: 13213.240 Max: 16504.801 Average: 14769.164	
BrentOilPrice	Real	0	Min: 19.330 Max: 127.980 Average: 73.435	
bi-7day-rr	Real	0	Min: 0.035 Max: 0.062 Average: 0.046	
inflation-rate	Real	0	Min: 0.013 Max: 0.059 Average: 0.029	

Showing attributes 1 - 10 Examples: 1,211 Special Attributes: 0 Regular Attributes: 10

Figure 14 Rapidminer Statistics Result of Integration and Imputed

Figure 15 Visualization Scatter Plot Research Datasets

4.4.2 Data transformation

Figure 14 shows there are large range differences between variables data. This will affect model building process. Therefore, data normalization required. Min-Max Normalization method is used, which transform values within specified range, minimum 0 and maximum 1 value are used. Figure

16 is the design process in Rapidminer. Results shown on Figure 17 and the statistic on Figure 18. Analysis relationship between variables using scatter plot shown on Figure 19.

Figure 16 Rapidminer Process Min-Max Normalization

Figure 17 shows a screenshot of the Rapidminer Results view for a dataset named 'ExampleSet (Normalize)'. The interface includes a top navigation bar with 'Design', 'Results', 'Turbo Prep', 'Auto Model', and 'Interactive Analysis' tabs. A sidebar on the left contains icons for Data, Statistics, Visualizations, and Annotations. The main area displays a table with 20 rows of data. The columns are: Row No., Open, High, Low, Close, Volume, USDIDR, BrentOilPrice, bi-7day-rr, inflation-r..., and Date. The data represents daily market information from July 1, 2019, to July 26, 2019. A filter at the top right indicates 'Filter (1,211 / 1,211 examples): all'. Below the table, it states 'ExampleSet (1,211 examples, 0 special attributes, 10 regular attributes)'.

Row No.	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume	USDIDR	BrentOilPrice	bi-7day-rr	inflation-r...	Date
1	0.701	0.682	0.706	0.699	0.181	0.276	0.421	0.909	0.432	Jul 1, 2019
2	0.703	0.682	0.705	0.700	0.182	0.285	0.396	0.909	0.432	Jul 2, 2019
3	0.696	0.679	0.696	0.694	0.159	0.299	0.409	0.909	0.432	Jul 3, 2019
4	0.696	0.679	0.703	0.698	0.199	0.293	0.405	0.909	0.432	Jul 4, 2019
5	0.699	0.679	0.704	0.697	0.188	0.285	0.413	0.909	0.432	Jul 5, 2019
6	0.695	0.674	0.693	0.691	0.145	0.262	0.412	0.909	0.432	Jul 8, 2019
7	0.693	0.680	0.701	0.701	0.168	0.296	0.413	0.909	0.432	Jul 9, 2019
8	0.705	0.687	0.713	0.707	0.161	0.311	0.439	0.909	0.432	Jul 10, 2019
9	0.714	0.694	0.714	0.709	0.172	0.288	0.434	0.909	0.432	Jul 11, 2019
10	0.711	0.691	0.706	0.697	0.189	0.277	0.436	0.909	0.432	Jul 12, 2019
11	0.709	0.695	0.717	0.710	0.198	0.239	0.434	0.909	0.432	Jul 15, 2019
12	0.711	0.692	0.712	0.705	0.168	0.213	0.414	0.909	0.432	Jul 16, 2019
13	0.705	0.684	0.708	0.703	0.204	0.242	0.408	0.909	0.432	Jul 17, 2019
14	0.702	0.686	0.708	0.705	0.219	0.246	0.392	0.818	0.432	Jul 18, 2019
15	0.712	0.700	0.720	0.721	0.183	0.230	0.397	0.818	0.432	Jul 19, 2019
16	0.724	0.704	0.721	0.714	0.177	0.221	0.404	0.818	0.432	Jul 22, 2019
17	0.719	0.700	0.714	0.705	0.183	0.238	0.410	0.818	0.432	Jul 23, 2019
18	0.710	0.689	0.709	0.700	0.217	0.251	0.404	0.818	0.432	Jul 24, 2019
19	0.704	0.687	0.711	0.705	0.175	0.247	0.406	0.818	0.432	Jul 25, 2019
20	0.701	0.679	0.690	0.683	0.171	0.255	0.406	0.818	0.432	Jul 26, 2019

Figure 17 Rapidminer Result of Integration and Normalized Data

Figure 18 shows a screenshot of the Rapidminer Statistics view for the same dataset. The interface is similar to Figure 17. The main area displays a summary table for 10 attributes. The columns are: Name, Type, Missing, Statistics (Min, Max, Average), and Filter (10 / 10 attributes). The attributes listed are Open, High, Low, Close, Volume, USDIDR, BrentOilPrice, bi-7day-rr, inflation-rate, and Date. The 'Date' attribute has a duration of 1824 days. At the bottom, it shows 'Showing attributes 1 - 10' and 'Examples: 1,211 Special Attributes: 0 Regular Attributes: 10'.

Name	Type	Missing	Min	Max	Average
Open	Real	0	0	1	0.705
High	Real	0	0	1	0.692
Low	Real	0	0	1	0.702
Close	Real	0	0	1	0.702
Volume	Real	0	0	1	0.225
USDIDR	Real	0	0	1	0.473
BrentOilPrice	Real	0	0	1	0.498
bi-7day-rr	Real	0	0	1	0.414
inflation-rate	Real	0	0	1	0.341
Date	Date	0	Earliest date Jul 1, 2019	Latest date Jun 28, 2024	Duration 1824 days

Figure 18 Rapidminer Statistics Result of Integration, Imputed, and Normalized

Figure 19 Visualization Scatter Plot Dataset Normalized

4.4.3 Data reduction

The data reduction step either in volume or dimension/variable is not required because both variables and the amount of data for each variable are complete for the model creation process.

4.4.4 Pre-processing results

The result of this data pre-processing step is a dataset in tabular form that has all input variables (X) and prediction variables (Y) namely the close variable. The variable name, input/target, and description explanation are explained in Table 8 Integrated Dataset Attributes. The datasets are filled with data according to the period from the data source and are ready for the next data mining process.

Table 8 Integrated Dataset Attributes

Variable Name	Variable	Description
Date		This is an index which is the identification of data rows using dates.
Open	X	This is the opening price of the IDX Composite on that date.
High	X	This is the highest price in IDX Composite trading on that date.
Low	X	This is the lowest price in IDX Composite trading on that date.
Close	Y (target)	This is the close price in IDX Composite trading on that date.
Volume	X	Number of shares traded on that date
USDIDR	X	USD to Rupiah exchange rate on that date
BrentOilPrice	X	World oil prices on that date

Variable Name	Variable	Description
bi-7day-rr	X	Bank Indonesia's interest rate on that date
inflation-rate	X	Indonesia's inflation rate on that date

4.5 Model Building

The model building process begins with the use of Rapidminer AI Studio software which is used to store the data repository of all research variables.

Process started with estimation methodologies for split datasets. Training datasets are then used in the model building process. Testing datasets will be used in the testing process to then test the model's performance.

4.5.1 Estimation methodologies

The study uses the simple split method to separate training data of 2/3 data and testing data of 1/3 data from datasets as shown on Figure 20.

Figure 20 Process Split Data Training dan Test

4.5.2 Process of model building

The model building process will use the neural net (NN) and deep learning (DL) algorithms available in the Rapidminer software. Figure 21 show the model building process in Rapidminer.

Figure 21 Rapidminer model building process

The first model is using the Neural Net algorithm which is one of the Predictive models provided by Rapidminer AI Studio. This Neural Net algorithm will use the following parameters (Figure 22):

- Hidden layer size = 2.
- Back-propagation learning process 200 times.
- The learning rate weight at each step is 0.01.
- Momentum fraction weight is 0.9.
- The sorted data will be randomized before the model learning process.

Result of the model is visualized in Figure 23.

Figure 22. Neural Net model building parameters

Figure 23. Neural Net model result

Then in the second model, namely Deep Learning, which is also one of the Predictive models provided by Rapidminer AI Studio, the parameters used are as follows (Figure 24):

- Activation uses the Rectifier Linear Unit (ReLU) function.
- Hidden layer sizes are 2 with 50 neurons each.
- Epochs, which is how many times the dataset must be iterated, this is set to 10.0.
- For advanced parameters, use the default values, namely: train sample per iteration = -2; epsilon = 1.0E-8; rho = 0.99; standardize = true; L1 = 1.0E-5; L2 = 0.0; max w2 = 10.0; loss function = automatic; distribution function = AUTO; missing values handling = MeanImputation; max runtime seconds = 0.
- Result of Deep Learning model is shown on Figure 25.

Figure 24. Deep Learning Model Building Parameters

Figure 25. Deep Learning Model Result

4.6 Testing and Evaluation

Testing is done on testing datasets using the results/model output from the model building process using training datasets. This is done on each Neural Net (NN) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithm operator as shown in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

Figure 26 Test Model Neural Net with Testing Datasets

Figure 27 Test Model Deep Learning with Testing Datasets

The output of labeled data from each model testing process is then used for the performance measurement process, this is done using the Performance (Regression) operator with the measurement criteria of RMSE, absolute error, squared error, and correlation (coefficient label and prediction) as seen in Figure 28.

Figure 28 Statistical Performance Evaluation Operators on Regression Predictions

Then the results of the statistical performance evaluation calculations of each neural network model are presented in Table 9. From these results, it is known that the RMSE result from NN model

result is 0.009, this value is smaller than the RMSE result from DL model result with value 0.016 (training dataset) and 0.014 (testing dataset).

Table 9 Performance Testing Prediction Model Results

	RMSE	Absolute Error	Squared Error	Correlation
Neural Net (NN)				
Training	0.009 +/- 0.000	0.007 +/- 0.006	0.000 +/- 0.000	0.999
Testing	0.009 +/- 0.000	0.007 +/- 0.005	0.000 +/- 0.000	0.999
Deep Learning (DL)				
Training	0.016 +/- 0.000	0.012 +/- 0.010	0.000 +/- 0.001	0.998
Testing	0.014 +/- 0.000	0.011 +/- 0.008	0.000 +/- 0.000	0.998

Performance results shows the RMSE of NN is 0.009 which is smaller than 0.016 (training) and 0.014 (testing) the RMSE of DL This means that the NN algorithm makes better predictions than DL

algorithm. Figure 29 shows the graphs of predicted versus the actual price for each NN model and DL model Figure 30.

Figure 29 Comparison of Neural Net Operator Prediction and Actual Values

Figure 30 Comparison of Deep Learning Operator Prediction and Actual Values

4.7 Deployment

After the evaluation results of the model have been obtained and the performance of its success rate is known. Then the results can be use as the basis to answer the formulation of the research problem.

ANN model with good performance then can be applied to an information system that predict IDX Composite closing price based on the input of technical factor parameters, namely: open, high, low, volume; and input of external factor parameters, namely: inflation rate, USD/IDR exchange rate, world oil prices, and BI-Rate. Figure 31 shows the prototype of the prediction application that. The ANN model from Rapidminer AI Studio deploy the model into Rapidminer AI hub. The Prediction IDX Composite (IHSG) application implemented with python programming language which integrate with ANN model webservice on Rapidminer AI Hub (requires a server and license).

Figure 31 Prototype UI of IDX Composite Close Prediction Application based on technical and external factors

4.8 Discussion

This research explore how ANN can be used to predict IDX Composite closing price using composite technical data and selected external factors data. Results shows that predictions using NN are 35% more accurate compare to DL with RMSE performance value of 0.009. NN prediction approach the actual closing price value. This performance gain illustrates the impact of incorporating novel aspect into the NN model use for predicting IDX Composite.

The research results are in line with the research question that prediction of the IDX Composite closing price with time-series data of technicals and selected external factors can be done using ANN

models accurately. This result also supports previous studies that use ANN to predict stock prices [18], [19], [20], [23] and supports on how the external factors affect the IDX Composite close price [2], [3], [5], [6].

The ANN Neural Net model then can be used and implemented into internal software of securities companies or other information system used by investors to support investment portfolio management decision making when composite technical factors and affecting factors are changing namely BI rates, inflation rates, world oil prices, and USD/IDR exchange rates. This study can serve as one of the topic's references of IDX Composite prediction using ANN and to support the use of the Neural Net algorithm to make predictions.

This research has limitations to be consider which first limitation is the data period used are in 5 years from July-2019 to July-2024. Second limitation is the selected affecting factors or variables are BI-Rate, inflation rates, USD/IDR rates, world oil prices, and composite technicals. Lastly is the Software being use which is Rapidminer AI-Studio along with the ANN model algorithms available in the software which is Neural Net and Deep Learning.

5 CONCLUSSION

From what has been discovered from this research that ANN with the Neural Net algorithm on the AI Studio software able accurately do prediction of IDX Composite closing price based on time-series of external variables namely: Bank Indonesia interest rates, inflation rates, world oil prices, USD/IDR exchange rates; and composite technical variables.

This research answers this research question How to forecast the IDX Composite utilizing time-series data of technical and external factor that affecting. This research also answer question about how accurate the models are. Neural Net algorithm has higher accuracy compared to Deep Learning algorithm. Visualization of the prediction results in relation to the actual value further illustrates this.

For future research author suggests conduct exploration using other factors that also affect IDX Composite, this includes combining fundamental aspects, technical aspects of stock analysis, and sentimental aspects. Another suggest is using other software for instance Google Tensorflow, Facebook PyTorch, Keras to create ANN models with the same variables.

In general, further research can focus on conducting ANN exploration to predict IDX Composite with the addition also combination other new factors, and experiments using other software tools.

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